

Open Repositories 2021 Conference Programme

Date: Monday, 07/June/2021

8:00am - 9:20am	Workshop: Lights and shadows in integrating and supporting ORCID in repository platforms <u>Alicia Fatima Gomez</u> ¹ , <u>Magdalena Andrae</u> ¹ , <u>Paloma Marin-Arraiza</u> ² 1: TU Wien, Austria; 2: ORCID, Spain	
8:00am - 10:50am	Workshop: Brokerage Event Towards a FAIR Compliant Commons in the ASREN Region <u>Yousef Torman</u> ¹ , <u>Abdullahi Behi Hussein</u> ² , <u>Ahmed Siyad</u> ² , <u>Alwaleed K. Alkhaja</u> ³ , <u>Anwaar Al Kandari</u> ⁴ , <u>Behailu Korma</u> ⁵ , <u>Daryl M. Grenz</u> ⁶ , <u>Helena Cousijn</u> ⁷ , <u>Hicham Boutracheh</u> ⁸ , <u>Margareth Gfrerer</u> ⁵ , <u>Mohamed Ali Ahmed</u> ² , <u>Raed Al-Zoubi</u> ¹ , <u>Rawia F. Radi</u> ⁹ , <u>Roberto Barbera</u> ¹⁰ , <u>Saida Messaoudi</u> ¹¹ , <u>Yassar Hanna Braik</u> ¹² 1: ASREN Arab States Research and Education, Jordan, Hashemite Kingdom of; 2: Somali Research and Education Network - SomaliREN; 3: Qatar National Library - QNL; 4: Kuwait Technical College - KTC; 5: Higher Education Strategy Center; 6: King Abdullah University for Science and Technology - KAUST; 7: Datacite; 8: Moroccan Institute of Scientific and Technical Information - IMIST; 9: Islamic University of Gaza (IUG); 10: University of Catania; 11: Institut National des Sciences et Technologies de la Mer - INSTM; 12: Syrian Virtual University - SVU	
9:30am - 10:50am	Workshop: How repositories can increase their FAIR share <u>Marjan Grootveld</u> ¹ , <u>Ilona von Stein</u> ¹ , <u>Linas Čepinskas</u> ¹ , <u>Patricia Herterich</u> ² , <u>Joy Davidson</u> ² 1: DANS - Data Archiving and Networked Services, The Netherlands; 2: Digital Curation Centre	
1:00pm - 2:20pm	Workshop: Introduction to Fedora 6.0 <u>David Wilcox</u> LYRISIS, Canada	Workshop: Making repositories part of your digital strategy: experience from the Samvera Community <u>Chris Awre</u> ¹ , <u>Karen Cariani</u> ² , <u>Nabeela Jaffer</u> ³ , <u>Alicia Morris</u> ⁴ 1: University of Hull, United Kingdom; 2: GBH; 3: University of Michigan; 4: Tufts University
1:00pm - 3:50pm	Workshop: Getting Started with DSpace 7.0: Basic Training <u>Tim Donohue</u> ¹ , <u>Art Lowel</u> ² , <u>Andrea Bollini</u> ³ 1: LYRISIS, United States of America; 2: Atmire, Belgium; 3: 4Science, Italy	
2:30pm - 3:50pm	Workshop: Europeana Data Model (EDM) Workflows in Archipelago <u>Diego A Pino Navarro</u> , <u>Allison K Lund</u> Metropolitan New York Library Council, United States of America	Workshop: Machine-Actionable DMPs in the Repository: Motivation and Implementation <u>Taylor Mudd</u> ¹ , <u>Richard Forrest</u> ² 1: Haplo, United Kingdom; 2: Cayuse

Date: Tuesday, 08/June/2021

1:00pm - 1:55pm 2:00pm - 2:45pm	Welcome & opening keynote: Sir Jeremy Farrar Ideas challenge introduction	
3:00pm - 3:55pm	Panel: Speaking up and speaking out - who will shape the narrative for OA repositories? <u>Kathleen Shearer</u> ¹ , <u>Eloy Rodrigues</u> ^{1,2} , <u>Johan Rooryck</u> ^{3,4} , <u>Dominique Bibini</u> ¹ 1: COAR, International; 2: University of Minho; 3: Leiden University; 4: cOAlition S	
4:00pm - 4:55pm	Presentations session 1 The Carolina Digital Repository During COVID-19: Responding to a Pandemic <u>Rebekah Kati</u> University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, United States of America CTDA in Context <u>Greg Colati</u> ¹ , <u>Michael Kemezis</u> ¹ , <u>Kayla Hinkson-Grant</u> ² 1: University of Connecticut, United States of America; 2: Mt. Holyoke College	Presentations session 2 Fedora Software and Community Update: All Aboard for Fedora 6.0 <u>David Wilcox</u> , <u>Arran Griffith</u> LYRISIS, Canada DSpace 7.0 : Coming to a DSpace near you <u>Tim Donohue</u> LYRISIS, United States of America

<p>5:00pm - 6:00pm</p>	<p>Connected in Science: How arXiv facilitates global interactions during the pandemic and beyond <u>Eleonora Presani</u> arXiv, United States of America</p> <p>Networking session</p>	<p>Islandora Community Update: Islandora at Home <u>Danny Lamb</u>¹, <u>Mark Jordan</u>² 1: Islandora Foundation, Canada; 2: Simon Fraser University</p>
<p>Date: Wednesday, 09/June/2021</p>		
<p>8:00am - 8:55am</p>	<p>24x7 session 1</p> <p>Context is as important as content — the Bridge of Knowledge platform as a comprehensive ecosystem of research information <u>Piotr Krajewski</u>, <u>Aleksander Mroziński</u> Gdańsk University of Technology, Poland</p> <p>Helda Open Books - A repository-based service bringing sold-out monographs and textbooks back to life <u>Markku Roinila</u>, <u>Jussi Piipponen</u> Helsinki university library, Finland</p> <p>8 Terabytes of Music to Explore with DSpace-GLAM and IIF: the Digital Library of the Milan Conservatory <u>Marta Crippa</u>², <u>Claudio Cortese</u>¹, <u>Emilia Groppo</u>¹, <u>Andrea Bollini</u>¹, <u>Riccardo Fazio</u>¹, <u>Francesco Pio Scognamiglio</u>¹ 1: 4Science, Italy; 2: Conservatorio "G. Verdi" di Milano, Italy</p> <p>OpenDOAR's repository assessment service (RAS) <u>Jennifer Sanchez-Davies</u> Jisc</p> <p>Sherpa Services – global collaboration for an enhanced and improved service <u>Karen Jackson</u> Jisc, United Kingdom</p> <p>Publications Router: populating repositories automatically <u>Steve Byford</u>¹, <u>Adam Rehin</u>¹, <u>Andrea Bollini</u>², <u>L. Andrea Pascarelli</u>², <u>Susanna Mornati</u>² 1: Jisc, UK; 2: 4Science, Italy</p> <p>Compliance without complaints <u>Taylor Mudd</u> Haplo, United Kingdom</p>	<p>Presentations session 3</p> <p>Development of National-level Institutional Repository Cloud Service for Open Science <u>Masaharu Hayashi</u>, <u>Yutaka Hayashi</u>, <u>Makoto Asaoka</u>, <u>Masashi Kawai</u>, <u>Yasuyuki Minamiyama</u>, <u>Kazutsuna Yamaji</u> National Institute of Informatics, Japan</p> <p>A shared governance and a sustainable funding model for HAL, the French National Open Archive <u>Bénédicte Kuntziger-Planche</u>, <u>Agnès Magron</u>, <u>Nathalie Fargier</u> Centre pour la Communication Scientifique Directe (CCSD) - CNRS, France</p> <p>Leveraging Open Services to Enhance Institutional Research Tracking Workflows <u>Yasmeen Alsaedi</u>, <u>Daryl Grenz</u>, <u>Mohamed Baessa</u> King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST), Saudi Arabia</p>
<p>9:00am - 9:55am</p>	<p>Presentations session 4</p> <p>Open for All? Addressing the Need for Regulating Access in the Disciplinary Repository PsychArchives</p>	

Lea Gerhards, Peter Weiland, Roland Ramthun, Christiane Baier
Leibniz Institute for Psychology (ZPID), Germany

4TU.ResearchData: Building the community

Connie Clare
4TU.ResearchData, Netherlands

Shared repositories: building (multi-tenancy) repository services at the British Library

Sara Gould, Jenny Basford, Torsten Reimer
The British Library, United Kingdom

9:00am **Developer track session 1**

CAPE: A javascript clientside repository

10:10am **Christopher James Gutteridge**
University of Southampton, United Kingdom

The IOI App: How and why to establish an institutional ORCID integration outside of your repository platform

Yasmeen Alsaedi, Daryl Grenz, Mohamed Baessa
King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST), Saudi Arabia

Developing COrDa: The COmmunity Orcid Dashboard

Adam Vials Moore¹, Monica Duke¹, Kirsty Wallis², Owen Stephens³
1: Jisc, United Kingdom; 2: University College London; 3: Owen Stephens Consulting Ltd

Two features, 10 lines of code

Taylor Mudd
Haplo, United Kingdom

Logical Item Filtering in DSpace

Kim Michael Shepherd, Pascal-Nicolas Becker
The Library Code GmbH

12:00pm **Minute Madness**

Status of students' graduation (masters) theses in repositories of six European universities

12:55pm **Danijel Gudelj¹, Ljiljana Poljak², Vicko Tomić¹, Mirta Matošić², Matko Marušić¹, Ana Marušić³**
1: ST-OPEN, University of Split, Split, Croatia; 2: Split University Library, Split, Croatia; 3: Department of Research in Biomedicine and Health, University of Split School of Medicine, Split, Croatia

Repositories and publishers: AgEcon Search forging new relationships

Linda Eells, Julie Kelly
University of Minnesota-United States of America

A Framework for an Arabic Terminology Management System (TMS) using Artificial Intelligence

Sherine Mahmoud Eid
Bibliotheca Alexandrina, Egypt

Advancing Hyku Project Update

Ellen Catz Ramsey¹, Brian Hole², Ilkay Holt³
1: University of Virginia, United States of America; 2: Ubiquity Press; 3: The British Library, United Kingdom

SANDIMS: South African National Geophysical Data and Instrumentation Management System

Kate Niemantingga, Pierre J Cilliers
South African National Space Agency, South Africa

Geodisy -- New geospatial data discovery for Canadian research data

Eugene Barsky

University of British Columbia, Canada

Understanding IR Impact: What Do Users Do with Our Stuff?

Wendy Walker

University of Montana, Missoula, United States of America

Atrium Repository: diffusion of cardiology knowledge

Francijane Oliveira da Conceição^{1,2}, **Cyntia Mendes Aguiar**^{1,2}, **Renato Cerceau**^{1,3}, **Jorge Zavaleta**⁴, **Cristiane da Cruz Lamas**^{1,2,5}

1: Instituto Nacional de Cardiologia - INC, Brazil; 2: Fundação Oswaldo Cruz - FIOCRUZ, Brazil; 3: Universidade Estadual do Rio de Janeiro, Brazil; 4: Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro - UFRJ, Brazil; 5: Universidade UNIGRANRIO, Brazil

RCIN - Digital Repository of Scientific Institutes in Poland

Błażej Betański, **Tomasz Parkola**, **Natalia Jeszke**

Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center, Poland

Changes and impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic response on Arca

Tiago Martins da Costa Ferreira, **Claudete Fernandes de Queiroz**, **Luciana Danielli de Araujo**, **Raphael Belchior Rodrigues**, **Éder de Almeida Freyre**, **Andréa Gonçalves do Nascimento**, **Angelo José Moreira Silva**, **Catarina Barreto Malheiro Pereira**, **Rita de Cassia da Silva**, **Leonardo Simonini Ferreira**

Fundação Oswaldo Cruz. Instituto de Comunicação e Informação Científica e Tecnológica em Saúde

Repository Re(volution): AgEcon Search Goes Global

Linda Eells, **Julie Kelly**

University of Minnesota-Waite Library, United States of America

PeruCRIS: A National Research Information Infrastructure based on DSpace-CRIS

Cesar Olivares¹, **Francisco Talavera**¹, **Abel del Carpio**¹, **Susanna Mornati**², **Andrea Bollini**², **Claudio Cortese**², **Corrado Lombardi**², **Alfonso Maza**³, **Ana Puentes de la Puebla**³

1: Concytec, Peru; 2: 4Science, Italy; 3: Semicrol, Spain

Availability of open government data in the Maghreb countries

Elsayed Elsayy¹, **Ahmed Maher Khafaga Shehata**²

1: Sultan Qaboos University, Oman, Tanta University (Egypt); 2: Sultan Qaboos University, Oman, Minia University (Egypt)

Sherpa Romeo – our roadmap

Karen Jackson, **Jane Anders**

Jisc, United Kingdom

Discovery after migration

Ben Summers, **Taylor Mudd**

Haplo, United Kingdom

Introduce Impact-Pathways in a CRIS – support societal impact orientation in research projects and funding processes

Birge Michaela Wolf¹, **Doris Lange**¹, **Thorsten Michaelis**¹, **Andrea Moser**¹, **Stefanie John**¹, **Andreas Abecker**², **Stefan Lossow**², **Lucia Hahne**², **Andrea Bollini**³, **Giuseppe Digilio**³, **Susanna Mornati**³

1: University of Kassel, Germany; 2: Disy; 3: 4Science

A Recommendation System for an Open Archive

Gulce Bal Bozkurt, Gozde Boztepe Karatas
Middle East Technical University, Turkey

The Scholarship of The Ohio State University: Open for All

Maureen Walsh
The Ohio State University, United States of America

Interoperability Standards for Distributed Collaboration in InvenioRDM

Sara Gonzales¹, Matthew B. Carson¹, Guillaume Viger¹, Lars Holm Nielsen², Kristi L. Holmes¹
1: Northwestern University, United States of America; 2: European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), Geneva, Switzerland

Zenodo spam detection using neural networks

Pablo Panero
CERN, Switzerland

DataCORE - Grappling With Big Files and Big Problems

James Halliday, Brian Keese
Indiana University, United States of America

Is it interoperability or is it integration?

Paul L.S. Stokes, Tamsin Burland, John Kaye, Howard Williams
Jisc, United Kingdom

Interoperability Intersection: Partnerships in Open Science Infrastructure

Eric Olson
Center for Open Science, United States of America

“Precedented”: Public Health, Open Access Infrastructure, and Interrogating Power in Repository Debates

Michael Scott¹, Kate Dohe²
1: Hispanic American Periodicals Index, UCLA; 2: University of Maryland Libraries

Bepress to DSpace in PJs: Migrating Two Open Repositories from Home

Julia Corrice, Chloe McLaren, Jim Del Rosso, Gail Steinhart
Cornell University Library, United States of America

1:00pm
-
2:25pm

Panel: Repository Rodeo

Maureen Walsh¹, Danny Brooke², Rory McNicholl³, Tim Shearer⁴, Taylor Mudd⁵, Sara Gonzales⁶, Arran Griffith⁷, Heather Greer Klein⁸
1: The Ohio State University, United States of America; 2: Harvard University, United States of America; 3: University of London, United Kingdom; 4: University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill, United States of America; 5: Haplo, United Kingdom; 6: Northwestern University, United States of America; 7: Islandora Foundation, Canada; 8: Samvera, United States of America

2:30pm
-
2:55pm

Panel: IRUS In Bloom: Expanded Openness for Institutional Repository Usage Statistics

Hannah Rosen¹, Laura Wong², Jim Ottaviani³
1: LYRASIS, United States of America; 2: Jisc, United Kingdom; 3: University of Michigan, United States of American

3:00pm
-
3:55pm

24x7 session 2

Elevating Open Data: Building an Accessible Environment for Data Stewardship in Research Libraries with CADRE

Jaci Wilkinson¹, Jamie V. Wittenberg², Patricia L. Mabry³, Valentin Pentchev⁴, Robert Van Rennes⁵, Ethan Fridmanski¹
1: Indiana University Libraries; 2: University Libraries, University of Colorado Boulder; 3: HealthPartners; 4:

Presentations session 5

Cataloging of Biological Datasets in AgDados - the Embrapa Data Repository

Marcia Izabel Fugisawa Souza, Antonio Nhani Junior, Poliana Fernanda Giachetto, Paula Regina Kuser-Falcao, Leandro Carrijo Cintra, Luiz Antonio Falaguasta Barbosa, Luiz Manoel Silva Cunha, Marcos Cezar Visoli, Tercia Zavaglia Torres
Embrapa Agricultural Informatics, Brazil

Indiana University Network Science Institute; 5: Big Ten Academic Alliance

Using Research Profiles as a Service (RPaS) to Populate an Institutional Repository

Agnes Gambill

Appalachian State University, United States of America

Swallow Beyond the Repository: Development of a Custom Metadata Management Software

Tomasz Neugebauer, Francisco Berrizbeitia

Concordia University, Canada

Repository Migration: How it started, How it's going

Nicholas Homenda, Juliet L. Hardesty

Indiana University Libraries, United States of America

Increasing the A in OA: How accessibility work in repositories should influence publisher agreements

Sadie Roosa

MIT Libraries, United States of America

We've got a Digital Repository: now what do we do with it?

Kent Douglas Reynolds, Bianca Parisi, Cindy Rigg

Niagara College Canada, Canada

Preserving Podcasts: An Institutional Repository Case Study

Erik A. Moore, Valerie M. Collins

University of Minnesota, United States of America

Hodgepodge or Showcase?

Gail McMillan

Virginia Tech, United States of America

4:00pm
-
4:55pm

24x7 session 3

Navigating OA eBook usage data stakeholder interests to facilitate cross-platform data exchange

Christina Drummond

Educopia Institute, United States of America

DataCite Service Providers program: Bringing the power of DOIs to a system near you

Liz Krznarich

DataCite, United States of America

Reopening the Repository: Redeveloping ScholarSphere to support Open Access

Daniel Coughlin, Seth Erickson, Adam Wead

Penn State University, United States of America

Sustaining Open Infrastructure Communities: Evaluating Fiscal and Administrative Service Options

Heather Greer Klein¹, Rosalyn Metz²

1: Samvera, United States of America; 2: Emory University, United States of America

An Engaged Campus Repository in Practice: The University of Minnesota's Institutional Repository and the Pandemic Response

Presentations session 6

Notify - The Repository and Services Interoperability Project

Kathleen Shearer¹, Martin Klein², Paul Walk¹

1: COAR, International; 2: Los Alamos National Laboratory, USA

On building a tool for finding datasets based on a list of researchers or publications

Washington L. R. Carvalho-Segundo¹, Thiago M. R. Dias²

1: Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology (IBICT), Brazil; 2: Federal Center for Technological Education of Minas Gerais (CEFET-MG), Brazil

From Hard Drives to Globus: Supporting new workflows for large data transfer in libraries

Kara Handren, Amber Leahey, Kaitlin Newson

Scholars Portal, Ontario Council of University Libraries, Canada

	<p>Erik A. Moore, Valerie M. Collins, Lisa R. Johnston University of Minnesota, United States of America</p> <p>Taking (small) steps towards accessible repository content Mariya Maistrovskaya University of Toronto Libraries, Canada</p> <p>5:00pm - 6:00pm Networking session</p> <p>10:00pm - 10:55pm Keynote: Dr Stephanie Russo Carroll</p> <p>11:00pm - 11:55pm Panel: "Broken for All": the case for persistent identifiers for digital cultural heritage resources Adrian Turner¹, Deborah Holmes-Wong², Zahid Rafique², John Kunze¹, Megan Lohnash³, Matthew McKinley⁴, Allison Lund⁵ 1: California Digital Library; 2: University of Southern California Libraries; 3: California Revealed; 4: Omeka; 5: Metropolitan New York Library Council</p>	<p>Presentations session 7</p> <p>Arkisto: a repository based platform for managing all kinds of research data <u>Peter Sefton</u>¹, <u>Marco La Rosa</u>², <u>Michael Lynch</u>¹ 1: University of Technology Sydney; 2: University of Melbourne</p> <p>Research Object Crate (RO-Crate) Update <u>Peter Sefton</u>¹, <u>Stian Soiland-Reyes</u>² 1: University of Technology Sydney; 2: The University of Manchester</p> <p>Next Generation Repositories: Best laid plans Tanya Holm University of New South Wales (UNSW), Sydney, Australia</p> <p>A Causal Analysis of the Progress of Green Open Access Masashi Kawai¹, Koichi Ojira¹, Jun Maeda², Masaki Nishizawa¹, Kazutsuna Yamaji¹ 1: National Institute of Informatics, Japan; 2: Hokkaido University</p>
Date: Thursday, 10/June/2021		
<p>12:00am - 12:55am</p>	<p>Developer track session 2</p> <p>Deploying a Serverless Application as a Docker Image <u>Terrence W Brady</u> California Digital Library, United States of America</p> <p>Live Demo: Create a Developer Workspace Challenge <u>Hardy Joseph Pottinger</u> California Digital Library, University of California, Office of the President, United States of America</p> <p>Building Scalable Serverless Digital Repositories using Amplify Open-source Framework <u>Yinlin Chen</u>, Tingting Jiang, Lee Hunter Virginia Tech, United States of America</p>	<p>Presentations session 8</p> <p>Repositories, are you ready to ROR? Maria Gould², <u>Liz Krznarich</u>¹, Daniella Lowenberg² 1: DataCite; 2: California Digital Library</p> <p>Next Generation Library Publishing project: Integrating open-source IR and publishing solutions <u>Catherine Mitchell</u>¹, <u>Katherine Skinner</u>², <u>Kristen Ratan</u>³ 1: California Digital Library, University of California; 2: Educopia Institute; 3: Stratos</p> <p>Dataset Search: An open source tool to support data discovery, reuse, and analytics</p>

	<p>Constructing a Repository Test Strategy Built on Docker Containers <u>Terrence W Brady</u> California Digital Library, United States of America</p>	<p><u>Sara Mannheimer</u>, <u>Jason A. Clark</u>, James Espeland, Jakob Schultz, Rhonda Borland, Kyle Hagerman, Daniel Laden Montana State University, United States of America</p>
8:00am - 8:55am	<p>Presentations session 9</p> <p>Plan S and Repository PIDs <u>Adam Vials Moore</u>¹, Sally Rumsey^{1,2}, James Kerwin³, Martin Wolf³ 1: Jisc, United Kingdom; 2: cOAlition S; 3: University of Liverpool</p> <p>Experience in Moving Toward An Open Repository For All <u>Tyng-Ruey Chuang</u>¹, Cheng-Jen Lee¹, Chia-Hsun Wang¹, Yu-Huang Wang² 1: Academia Sinica, Taiwan; 2: Independent Scholar</p> <p>Plan S and Open Access via repositories: Unity in diversity <u>Johan Rooryck</u>¹, <u>Sally Rumsey</u>² 1: Leiden University, cOAlition S; 2: Jisc, cOAlition S</p>	<p>Presentations session 10</p> <p>Results from the OpenAIRE Call for Innovation: Enrich local data via the OpenAIRE Graph <u>Andrea Bollini</u>¹, Susanna Mornati¹, Giuseppe Digilio¹, Jordan Piščanc², Michele Artini³, Claudio Atzori³ 1: 4Science, Italy; 2: University of Trieste, Italy; 3: ISTI-CNR, Italy</p> <p>ORCID and OpenAIRE Compliance for DSpace <u>Courtney Earl Matthews</u>¹, William Roy¹, Andrea Bollini², L. Andrea Pascarelli², <u>Susanna Mornati</u>², Kathleen Shearer³, Pierre Lasou⁴ 1: Queen's University Library, Canada; 2: 4Science, Italy; 3: COAR; 4: Université Laval</p> <p>How to ensure "good" data? Quality assurance by research data repositories <u>Maxi Kindling</u>, <u>Dorothea Strecker</u>, Vivien Petras, Yi Wang Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin, Berlin School of Library and Information Science, Germany</p>
9:00am - 9:55am	<p>24x7 session 4</p> <p>Ready-made or tailor-made? Seeking seamless depositing solutions for multi (LMIC) country qualitative data <u>Moni Choudhury</u>¹, Hani Salim^{1,2}, Hana Mahmood³, Dhiraj Agarwal⁴, Tathagata Bhattacharjee^{4,5}, John Norrie¹, Sanjay Juvekar⁴ 1: University of Edinburgh, United Kingdom; 2: Universiti Putra Malaysia, Malaysia; 3: Neoventive Solutions, Pakistan; 4: KEMHRC, Pune, India; 5: LSHTM, United Kingdom</p> <p>Interoperability as a service Tamsin Margaret Burland, John Kaye, Paul Stokes, Howard Williams Jisc, United Kingdom</p> <p>Would auto-translation of metadata enhance discovery and impact of research data? Paul L. S. Stokes, Tamsin Burland, John Kaye, Howard Williams Jisc, United Kingdom</p> <p>Lessons learnt in setting up a "one person repository" Ravi Murugesan Auroville, India</p> <p>Pavia Digital Library: enhancing and supporting interoperability within the Cultural Heritage Domain with DSpace-GLAM</p>	<p>Presentations session 11</p> <p>DSpace-CRIS 7 is here! <u>Andrea Bollini</u>, Mykhaylo Boychuk, Pasquale Cavallo, Claudio Cortese, Giuseppe Digilio, Riccardo Fazio, Damiano Fiorenza, Luca Giamminonni, Corrado Lombardi, Alessandro Martelli, Luigi Andrea Pascarelli, Matteo Perelli, Francesco Pio Scognamiglio, Susanna Mornati 4Science, Italy</p> <p>DSpace 7 - Enhanced Submission & Workflow Andrea Bollini, <u>Giuseppe Digilio</u>, Claudio Cortese 4Science, Italy</p> <p>DSpace 7 - Configurable Entities <u>Lieven Droogmans</u>, Ben Bosman Atmire, Belgium</p>

<p>12:00pm - 12:55pm</p>	<p>Gabriele Rossini², Paolo Nassi², Roberto Canevari², Massimo Aurelio², <u>Claudio Cortese¹</u>, Emilia Groppo¹, Andrea Bollini¹, Riccardo Fazio¹, Matteo Perelli¹, Francesco Pio Scognamiglio¹ 1: 4Science, Italy; 2: Università degli Studi di Pavia, Italy</p> <p>Breaking language barriers <u>Bram Luyten</u> Atmire, Belgium</p> <p>A National PID Landscape and Beyond <u>Adam Vials Moore¹</u>, Monica Duke¹, Balviar Notay¹, Christopher Brown¹, Alice Meadows², Josh Brown² 1: Jisc, United Kingdom; 2: MoreBrains Cooperative</p> <p>Networking session</p>	
<p>1:00pm - 1:55pm</p>	<p>Keynote: Dr Bianca Amaro</p>	
<p>2:00pm - 2:55pm</p>	<p>Panel: Dataverse Community & CoreTrustSeal: Certifying generalist data repositories <u>Katherine Mika¹</u>, <u>Sonia Barbosa¹</u>, <u>Philipp Conzett²</u>, <u>Robert R. Downs³</u>, <u>Jonathan Crabtree⁴</u>, <u>Ceilyn Boyd¹</u>, Merce Crosas¹ 1: Harvard University; 2: UiT The Arctic University of Norway; 3: Center for International Earth Science Information Network (CIESIN), Columbia University; 4: Odum Institute, University of North Carolina Chapel Hill</p>	<p>Presentations session 12 Open for all. Reusable for whom? A review of what data reusers want and how data repositories can deliver <u>Lisa R Johnston¹</u>, <u>Ixchel M Faniel²</u>, <u>Katie Wisse³</u> 1: University of Minnesota, United States of America; 2: OCLC Research, United States of America; 3: New York University</p> <p>Open for all but for how long? Roles, responsibilities and accountabilities in the preservation of research data <u>Amy Currie</u>, <u>William Kilbride</u> Digital Preservation Coalition, United Kingdom</p> <p>The Entity-Relation Metamodel from Repositories to Aggregators - The case of LA Referencia and RCAAP jointship Project <u>José Carvalho¹</u>, Lautaro Matas², Washington Segundo³, Paulo Graça⁴, Paulo Lopes⁴ 1: University of Minho, Portugal; 2: LA Referencia; 3: IBICT; 4: FCT FCCN</p>
<p>3:00pm - 4:00pm</p>	<p>Closing & Ideas challenge</p>	